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PART 4 OF SECOND REPORT OF THE ULTRA SHORT WAVE
PROPAGATION PANEL WORKING COMMITTEE.

PAPER AC.8250/USW.144.

CONFIDENTIAL.

ATTENUATION OF CENTIMETRE AND MILLIMETRE
WAVES BY RAIN, HAIL, FOGS AND CLOUDS.

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The Report came to me from Peter Ryde, son of the authors John W. Ryde and his wife Dorothy, who was a first cousin of my father. She performed much of the mathematical work, and it was amongst her belongings when she died. The image quality is about the best that could be produced, given the age of the paper and its general condition, plus the fact that it was typed and printed by the wax stencil process in common use at the time.

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RESEARCH
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PAPER AC.8250/US7.144.

ATTENUATION OF CENTIMETRE AND MILLIMETRE
WAVES BY RAIN, HAIL, FOGS AND CLOUDS.

This report is a continuation of previous Reports Nos. 7831 and 8516 and gives the computed attenuations produced by various meteorological conditions, for both the cm. and mm. bands.

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SUMMARY.

Using the latest experimental values for the refractive index and absorption index of water and ice for the relevant wavelengths, the computation of the attenuation resulting from rain, hail, fogs and clouds has been investigated in greater detail than previously. The effect of temperature has also been fully investigated for the first time.

The attenuation due to rain at 18° C. is given in Table IX and Figure (6) for the range $\lambda = 0.3$ to $\lambda = 10$ cm. and for intensities from 0.25 to 150 mm./hr. For $\lambda = 1.25$ and $\lambda = 3$ the new values lie within the limits previously given. At shorter wavelengths the values are less than those given by linear extrapolation.

Excellent agreement is found between the predicted values and the recent B.T.L. observations, which have now been carried out at wavelengths down to 0.6 cm. The comparison is seen in Figure (7). Predicted curves for still shorter wavelengths will be found on Figure (8).

The effect of temperature changes from 10° to 30° C. is small at $\lambda = 1.25$ and 3 cms. and does not affect the comparison with the B.T.L. observations. The temperature effect becomes more appreciable towards 0° and above 30° C. Temperature correction factors for various wavelengths and rates of precipitation are given in Table XVI. For $\lambda = 0.5, 1.25, 3.2$ and 10 cm. the attenuations are given directly for each 10° between 0° C. and 40° C. in Tables XII to XV.

The attenuation due to fogs and clouds of given liquid water content, M gm. per m.³, is given in Table X for wavelengths from 0.1 cm. up to 10 cm. Table XI gives the likely range of attenuation to be associated with a given visual range in the case of $\lambda = 0.5, 1.25$ and 3.0 cm.

The effect of temperature in the case of fogs and clouds is only slightly dependent on wavelength; in each case the attenuation falls as the temperature rises. Roughly, the values of attenuation at 0° and 40° C. are respectively twice and half those at 18° C.

In Table XVIII we give values of the attenuation produced by hailstones of diameters between 0.05 and 4.0 cms., for the standard concentration of one stone per cubic centimetre. Next, we desire the attenuation in db./km. produced by a rate of precipitation of hail which, if the ice were converted to liquid, would amount to 1 mm./hr. of water. No size-distribution functions for hailstones are available but it is shown that a fair estimate of the attenuation due to any actual precipitation may be found by multiplying the observed equivalent precipitation by the appropriate k value of Table XIX.

A comparison, in Table XX, of the attenuation due to rain and hail shows that for $\lambda = 3$ to 10 cm. the values for hail are between 1/10th and 1/100th those for rain with the same precipitation rate and the same drop diameter. At $\lambda = 0.5$ cm., however, we find that, for diameters from 0.3 to 0.5 cm., hail is rather more effective than rain.

The temperature effect is found to be negligible for hailstorms when the wavelength is 1.25 cm. or less, but it may become significant for storms composed of small hailstones when λ is equal to or greater than 3 cms.

As regards clouds composed of ice particles, it is shown that, for wavelengths near 1 cm., the attenuation of such clouds at -40° C. is of the order of 1/2000th that due to liquid droplet clouds at 0° C.; it may therefore almost always be neglected.

The last section gives information on the higher rates of precipitation that may be experienced for various durations. The world record for short period rain is a 2-hour storm during which the precipitation rate rose to 1,260 mm./hr. for a period of 3 minutes. Attenuations, which are attained or exceeded, over given durations, with various frequencies, may be read directly from Figures 11 and 12.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Since the publication of Report No. 8516, new values of the basic refractive and absorption indices, n and n_k respectively, have been determined by Sexton⁽¹⁾ for water between 0° C. and 40° C. and by Dunsmuir and Lamb⁽²⁾ for ice between -50° C. and 0° C.

In the case of water, the new values differ slightly from those used in the previous report and entail certain modifications of the results there given. For ice, on the other/

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- (1) J.A.Sexton. The Dielectric Properties of Water at Wavelengths from 2 mm. to 10 cm. and over the Temperature Range 0° C. to 40° C. N.P.I. Paper No. R.R.B./C.115, March 1945.
- (2) R.Dunsmuir and J.Lamb. The Dielectric Properties of Ice at Wavelengths of 3 and 9 cms. Manchester University Report No. 61, March 1945.

Note: The above two papers form Parts 2 and 3 of the Second Report of the Ultra Short Wave Propagation Panel Working Committee.

other hand, the values differ considerably from the old, but the changes are of such a nature that the final results are of the same order of magnitude as before.

Since, for water, the experimental values which are for the range $\lambda = 1$ to 10 cm., fit closely an expression of the Debye form, we have used, for wavelengths in the millimetre band, values of n and $n \times$, predicted from this expression. For ice, the experiments show no measurable change between $\lambda = 3$ and 10 cm. and it is to be expected that the observed constants will also hold for wavelengths some way below this.

Using the new data, the computation of the resulting attenuation from rain, clouds and hail, has been carried much further than previously. The wavelength range has been extended over the millimetre band and a much greater number of values have been computed from the exact expressions (12) to (16) of Report No. 7831. The effect of temperature variations has also been worked out.

As in the previous report, the attenuation is first expressed as the db. loss per km. for a concentration of one drop per cm.³ ($N = 1$), for a range of drop diameters. In the case of rain, these figures are then used to find, for each drop diameter, the attenuation that would be produced by rain composed of drops all of which are of the given size. Finally, by combining the latter values with drop size distributions typical of different rates of precipitation, the attenuation is related directly to the intensity of rainfall.

For this purpose the somewhat limited set of drop-size distributions, due to Lenard, which were used previously, has been replaced by the more comprehensive data recently published by Laws and Parsons⁽³⁾. No similar data is available for hailstorms, so that our results can be given only for storms assumed to be composed of hail stones of constant diameter. The attenuation due to fogs and clouds has been re-computed with the new data and the temperature effect has been studied in this case also.

2. VALUES OF THE REFRACTIVE AND ABSORPTION INDICES.

The basic data regarding the Refractive and Absorption Indices, taken from the above mentioned reports by Sexton and by Dunsmuir and Lamb, are given in Tables I and II. The 18° C. value for water has been interpolated. These constants have been used throughout the present report.

Table I/

(3) J.O.Laws and D.A.Persons. The Relation of Drop Size to Intensity. Washington. Trans. Amer. Geoph. Union. p.452 (1943).

Table I.

Refractive and Absorption Indices for Water (Saxton).

T° C.	λ = 0.5 cm.		λ = 1.24 cm.		λ = 3.2 cm.		λ = 10 cm.	
	n	nχ	n	nχ	n	nχ	n	nχ
0	3.18	1.76	4.68	2.73	7.10	2.89	8.99	1.47
10	3.80	2.25	5.74	2.92	8.00	2.33	9.02	0.90
18	4.21	2.51	6.4	2.8	8.30	1.90	8.9	0.69
20	4.39	2.54	6.53	2.77	8.33	1.72	8.88	0.63
30	4.94	2.67	7.10	2.48	8.39	1.31	8.71	0.45
40	5.47	2.69	7.47	2.11	8.35	1.02	8.53	0.36

Table II.

Refractive and Absorption Indices for Ice.

λ = 3.0 to 10 cm. (Dunsmuir and Lemb).

T° C.	n	nχ
0°	1.75	0.00105
-10	1.75	0.000285
-30	1.75	0.000145
-50	1.75	0.000110

For wavelengths not represented in Table I, values have been found from the Debye theory using the relations (27) to (30) of Report No. 8516 but with new constants deduced from Saxton's results and given in Table III.

Table III.

Constants for the Debye Relations (Water).

T° C.	ε ₀	ε ₁	k
0	5.5	88	3.59
10	5.5	84	2.24
18	5.5	81	1.66
20	5.5	80	1.53
30	5.5	76.4	0.112
40	5.5	73	0.0859

The corresponding values of n, nχ, g and h for water at 18° C. are given in Table IV. The last column gives the value of the constant,

$$C_1 = \frac{6h}{(g+2)^2 + h^2}$$

$$g = n^2(1 - \chi^2)$$

$$h = 2n^2\chi$$

..... (1)

or/

of Reports Nos. 7831 and 8516. Although Sexton's measurements extend only down to $\lambda = 1.24$ cm., the satisfactory fit to the Debye curves gives confidence in the values for the lower wavelengths. In what follows, this will be seen to be confirmed by the good agreement found between the predicted attenuation and the observations by B.T.L. at $\lambda = 0.6$ cm. It is therefore reasonable to expect that the effects we shall compute for still lower wavelengths will be, at least, of the right order of magnitude.

Table IV.

Values of n , $n\lambda$, g , h and c_1 for water at 18° C.

λ cm.	n	$n\lambda$	g	h	c_1
0.1	2.56	0.880	5.79	4.50	0.334
0.2	2.98	1.51	6.59	9.00	.349
0.3	3.41	1.94	7.87	13.22	.291
0.4	3.83	2.24	9.65	17.13	.242
0.5	4.21	2.51	11.38	21.2	.202
0.6	4.60	2.63	14.25	24.2	.171
0.7	4.93	2.73	16.83	26.9	.150
0.8	5.26	2.81	19.80	29.6	.131
0.9	5.55	2.85	22.7	31.6	.118
1.0	5.82	2.87	25.6	33.4	.107
1.1	6.02	2.94	27.6	35.4	.0998
1.2	6.30	2.85	31.5	35.8	.0894
1.25	6.40	2.80	33.1	35.8	.0854
2.0	7.50	2.48	50.1	37.2	.0545
3.0	8.18	1.96	63.1	32.1	.0366
5.0	8.67	1.30	73.5	22.6	.0218
10.0	8.90	0.69	78.8	12.3	.0110

3. THE COMPUTATION SCHEME.

It was shown in Report No. 8516, Section 3, that if centimetre units are used for the drop diameter D and wavelength λ , the attenuation in db. per km. may be expressed in the form

$$\frac{dB}{km} = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 \sigma \quad \dots(2)$$

while in Report No. 7831 it is shown that

$$\sigma = \frac{N \lambda^2}{2\pi} A_i \quad \dots(3)$$

where/

where N is the number of drops per cubic centimetre and A_i is the imaginary part of

$$\sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} (-1)^{\nu} (a_{\nu} - p_{\nu}) \quad \dots (4)$$

in which a_{ν} and p_{ν} are complex functions of n , $n\lambda$ and D/λ given by expressions (13) to (16) of Report No. 7831.

In the present report it will be convenient to write

$$A_i = f_i(\alpha, n, \lambda) \equiv f_i(\alpha) \quad \dots (5)$$

where
$$\alpha = \frac{\pi D}{\lambda} \quad \dots (6)$$

Then for a concentration of 1 drop per cm.^3 ($N = 1$) the attenuation will be

$$\frac{dI}{I \, km}_{(N=1)} = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 \cdot \frac{\lambda^2}{2\pi} f_i(\alpha) \quad \dots (7)$$

In Report No. 8516, Section 3, a simple series form was given, by means of which $f_i(\alpha)$ can be found for small values of α . For the large values of n and $n\lambda$ needed here this series is unreliable for values of α greater than about 0.1 so that, for the present work, it was necessary to evaluate $f_i(\alpha)$ exactly, by means of (3) and the partial wave coefficients a_{ν} and p_{ν} .

For the computation of a_{ν} and p_{ν} the expressions (14) and (15) of Report No. 7831 were first resolved into real and imaginary parts. Assuming for the moment that

$$m = n - i n \lambda \quad \dots (8)$$

is real we obtain

$$a_{\nu} = (-1)^{\nu} (2\nu+1) \frac{P_{\nu} - m Q_{\nu}}{(R_{\nu} - m Q_{\nu})^2 + X_{\nu}^2} F_{\nu} \quad \dots (9)$$

$$p_{\nu} = (-1)^{\nu+1} (2\nu+1) \frac{P_{\nu} - \frac{1}{m} Q_{\nu}}{(R_{\nu} - \frac{1}{m} Q_{\nu})^2 + X_{\nu}^2} F'_{\nu} \quad \dots (10)$$

in which

$$F_{\nu} = \left[\left\{ T_{\nu} (R_{\nu} - m Q_{\nu}) + X_{\nu} Y_{\nu} \right\} + i \left\{ Y_{\nu} (R_{\nu} - m Q_{\nu}) - X_{\nu} T_{\nu} \right\} \right] \dots (11)$$

and

$$F'_{\nu} = \left[\left\{ T_{\nu} (R_{\nu} - \frac{1}{m} Q_{\nu}) + X_{\nu} Y_{\nu} \right\} + i \left\{ Y_{\nu} (R_{\nu} - \frac{1}{m} Q_{\nu}) - X_{\nu} T_{\nu} \right\} \right] \dots (12)$$

where/

where

$$Q_v = \frac{S_v(m\alpha)}{S'_v(m\alpha)} \quad \dots (13)$$

and where the following are independent of m ,

$$P_v = \frac{S_v(\alpha)}{S'_v(\alpha)} \quad R_v = \frac{C_v(\alpha)C'_v(\alpha) + S_v(\alpha)S'_v(\alpha)}{|E'_v(\alpha)|^2} \quad \dots (14)$$

$$T_v = \frac{C'_v(\alpha)S'_v(\alpha)}{|E'_v(\alpha)|^2} \quad Y_v = \frac{\{S'_v(\alpha)\}^2}{|E'_v(\alpha)|^2} \quad \dots (15)$$

$$X_v = \frac{1}{|E'_v(\alpha)|^2} \quad \dots (16)$$

In these expressions $S_v(\alpha)$, $C_v(\alpha)$ and $E_v(\alpha) = C_v(\alpha) - iS_v(\alpha)$ are Riccati-Bessel Functions and the primed values are their first derivatives with respect to α .

If now we put m in its complex form (8), expressions (14) to (16) are unaffected but the argument of Q_v becomes complex. The next step was to prepare schedules for the computation of $S_v(x)$ and $S'_v(x)$ for complex arguments in order to obtain

$$mQ_v = G_{a,v} - iH_{a,v} \quad \dots (17)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{m}Q_v = G_{p,v} - iH_{p,v} \quad \dots (18)$$

Then, substituting in (11) and (12) we have

$$a_v = (-1)^v (2v+1) \frac{\phi_{a,v} + i\psi_{a,v}}{\theta_{a,v}} \quad \dots (19)$$

$$p_v = (-1)^{v+1} (2v+1) \frac{\phi_{p,v} + i\psi_{p,v}}{\theta_{p,v}} \quad \dots (20)$$

where/

where

$$\phi_{a,\nu} = \left\{ (R_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu})^2 + (X_{\nu} - H_{a,\nu})^2 \right\} \left[(R_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu}) \{ T_{\nu} (P_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu}) - H_{a,\nu} Y_{\nu} \} + (X_{\nu} + H_{a,\nu}) \{ Y_{\nu} (P_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu}) + H_{a,\nu} T_{\nu} \} \right]. \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma_{a,\nu} = \left\{ (R_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu})^2 + (X_{\nu} - H_{a,\nu})^2 \right\} \left[(R_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu}) \{ Y_{\nu} (P_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu}) + H_{a,\nu} T_{\nu} \} - (X_{\nu} + H_{a,\nu}) \{ T_{\nu} (P_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu}) - H_{a,\nu} Y_{\nu} \} \right] \dots \quad (22)$$

$$\theta_{a,\nu} = \left\{ (R_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu})^2 + X_{\nu}^2 - H_{a,\nu}^2 \right\}^2 + 4 H_{a,\nu}^2 (R_{\nu} - G_{a,\nu})^2 \dots \quad (23)$$

and in which the corresponding expressions for p_{ν} are obtained by using $G_{p,\nu}$ and $H_{p,\nu}$ in place of $G_{a,\nu}$ and $H_{a,\nu}$.

The series (4) converges fairly rapidly for the smaller values of α but for the larger values it first diverges but ultimately becomes convergent. We have found that, for an error of less than 1%, it is necessary to proceed as far as $\nu = 10$ for $\alpha = 6$ and to $\nu = 15$ for $\alpha = 10$.

Certain polynomial and series expressions, for Q_{ν} and P_{ν} , can be obtained which, for small α and n , are simpler than the above scheme and are valuable in special cases. An example of these is the simple series given in Appendix (I) of Report No. 7831. But for the high values of n , $n\lambda$ and α which concern us here we find the method we have outlined is preferable. This is particularly the case as a more detailed study shows that there are certain valuable approximations which can be used to shorten the work in some cases, although it is then necessary to check that the errors involved are negligible.

4. THE ATTENUATION FOR WATER DROPS AT A CONCENTRATION OF ONE PER CM.³ (N = 1) AND AT 18° C.

The computations described above have now been completed for water for a number of values of α at each of the wavelengths 0.3, 0.5, 1.0, 1.25 and 3.0 cms. Curves of $f_1(\alpha)$ and $\log f_1(\alpha)$ were then plotted for each wavelength. Figure (1) shows, for example, the curve for $\lambda = 0.3$ cm.

Values of $f_1(\alpha)$ corresponding, at each wavelength, to a series of equally spaced drop diameters were read off

and/

and were then substituted in equation (7) to give the db. loss per km. The results are given in Table V and are shown graphically in Figure (2). The values for $\lambda = 0.4, 0.6$ and 3.2 cm. were found by interpolation while those for $\lambda = 10$ and for less than 0.1 , at all wavelengths, were determined directly from the series (2) of Report No. 8516.

Table V.
db. loss per km. for water at 18°C . for various drop diameters and wavelengths and a concentration of 1 drop per cm^3 .

$\frac{\lambda}{D}$ cm. cm.	Limit $\frac{D}{\lambda} \rightarrow \infty$	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	1.0	1.25	3.0	3.2	10
0.05	$8.54 \cdot 10^2$	$8.34 \cdot 10^2$	$5.80 \cdot 10^2$	$3.46 \cdot 10^2$	$1.74 \cdot 10^2$	$5.62 \cdot 10^1$	$2.71 \cdot 10^1$	4.21	3.55	$2.94 \cdot 10^{-1}$
0.10	$3.42 \cdot 10^3$	$9.02 \cdot 10^3$	$6.80 \cdot 10^3$	$4.67 \cdot 10^3$	$3.10 \cdot 10^3$	$1.00 \cdot 10^3$	$6.25 \cdot 10^2$	$5.05 \cdot 10^1$	4.47 10	2.53
0.15	$7.68 \cdot 10^3$	$2.18 \cdot 10^4$	$2.12 \cdot 10^4$	$2.04 \cdot 10^4$	$1.85 \cdot 10^4$	$6.91 \cdot 10^3$	$4.19 \cdot 10^3$	$4.16 \cdot 10^2$	$3.24 \cdot 10^2$	9.39
0.20	$1.37 \cdot 10^4$	$4.07 \cdot 10^4$	$4.03 \cdot 10^4$	$3.97 \cdot 10^4$	$3.85 \cdot 10^4$	$2.76 \cdot 10^4$	$1.37 \cdot 10^4$	$2.21 \cdot 10^3$	$1.70 \cdot 10^3$	$2.49 \cdot 10^1$
0.25	$2.14 \cdot 10^4$	$6.35 \cdot 10^4$	$6.31 \cdot 10^4$	$6.22 \cdot 10^4$	$6.15 \cdot 10^4$	$5.53 \cdot 10^4$	$4.00 \cdot 10^4$	$6.98 \cdot 10^3$	$5.75 \cdot 10^3$	$5.61 \cdot 10^1$
0.30	$3.07 \cdot 10^4$	$8.90 \cdot 10^4$	$8.87 \cdot 10^4$	$8.81 \cdot 10^4$	$8.79 \cdot 10^4$	$8.50 \cdot 10^4$	$7.60 \cdot 10^4$	$1.56 \cdot 10^4$	$1.40 \cdot 10^4$	$1.13 \cdot 10^2$
0.35	$4.20 \cdot 10^4$	$1.18 \cdot 10^5$	$1.19 \cdot 10^5$	$1.21 \cdot 10^5$	$1.22 \cdot 10^5$	$1.21 \cdot 10^5$	$1.15 \cdot 10^5$	$2.76 \cdot 10^4$	$2.54 \cdot 10^4$	$2.09 \cdot 10^2$
0.40	$5.46 \cdot 10^4$	$1.52 \cdot 10^5$	$1.53 \cdot 10^5$	$1.56 \cdot 10^5$	$1.57 \cdot 10^5$	$1.58 \cdot 10^5$	$1.55 \cdot 10^5$	$4.35 \cdot 10^4$	$3.98 \cdot 10^4$	$3.65 \cdot 10^2$
0.45	$6.93 \cdot 10^4$	$1.90 \cdot 10^5$	$1.92 \cdot 10^5$	$1.94 \cdot 10^5$	$1.95 \cdot 10^5$	$1.98 \cdot 10^5$	$1.95 \cdot 10^5$	$6.35 \cdot 10^4$	$5.75 \cdot 10^4$	$6.10 \cdot 10^2$
0.50	$8.54 \cdot 10^4$	$2.26 \cdot 10^5$	$2.32 \cdot 10^5$	$2.35 \cdot 10^5$	$2.39 \cdot 10^5$	$2.42 \cdot 10^5$	$2.38 \cdot 10^5$	$8.68 \cdot 10^4$	$7.94 \cdot 10^4$	$9.76 \cdot 10^2$
0.55	$1.035 \cdot 10^5$	$2.68 \cdot 10^5$	$2.77 \cdot 10^5$	$2.85 \cdot 10^5$	$2.91 \cdot 10^5$	$2.94 \cdot 10^5$	$2.84 \cdot 10^5$	$1.13 \cdot 10^5$	$1.05 \cdot 10^5$	$1.51 \cdot 10^3$
0.60	$1.23 \cdot 10^5$	$3.07 \cdot 10^5$	$3.22 \cdot 10^5$	$3.37 \cdot 10^5$	$3.48 \cdot 10^5$	$3.53 \cdot 10^5$	$3.30 \cdot 10^5$	$1.43 \cdot 10^5$	$1.38 \cdot 10^5$	$2.24 \cdot 10^3$
0.65	$1.45 \cdot 10^5$	$3.46 \cdot 10^5$	$3.75 \cdot 10^5$	$3.97 \cdot 10^5$	$4.15 \cdot 10^5$	$4.20 \cdot 10^5$	$3.89 \cdot 10^5$	$1.74 \cdot 10^5$	$1.73 \cdot 10^5$	$3.16 \cdot 10^3$

For the larger drops, Figure (2) shows clearly that the attenuation first increases as the wavelength is reduced, then passes through a maximum which, for the largest drops ($D \sim 0.6$ cm.) is in the neighbourhood of $\lambda = 0.8$ cm. For very small drops the attenuation increases steadily as the wavelength is decreased down to $\lambda = 0.3$ cm., but for these cases also there must, in general, be a maximum. This follows because, for the limiting condition, $D/\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ we have,

$$\frac{dl}{k_m(N=1)} = 4.343 \cdot 10^5 \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \dots (24)$$

$$(D/\lambda \rightarrow \infty)$$

and values determined from this relation, which are given in Table V and shown at the left hand side of Figure (2), are lower than those for $\lambda = 0.3$ cm.

5. ATTENUATION FOR RAIN OF CONSTANT D.

As a step towards the relation of the attenuation for $N = 1$ to that for actual rainstorms, we must find, for each drop diameter, what rate of precipitation corresponds to the concentration of one drop per cm.³.

In report No. 8516, Section (7), it is shown that, if p is the rate of precipitation in mm. per hour, then

$$p = 1.885 \cdot 10^6 v N D^3 \dots (24)$$

where v is the terminal velocity of the drops in metres per second. Values of the terminal velocities have been provided by Best⁽⁴⁾. This data is to be preferred to the older figures of Lenard, which were used in Report No. 8516, and has been used for the present work. The values are given in Table VI, which also gives the corresponding values of p for $N = 1$. The values for the largest diameters have been extrapolated.

Table VI.

Terminal Velocity and Rate of Precipitation
for $N = 1$.

D cm.	v m. per sec.	p (for $N=1$) mm. per hr.
.05	2.1	$4.94 \cdot 10^2$
.10	3.9	$7.35 \cdot 10^3$
.15	5.3	$3.38 \cdot 10^4$
.20	6.4	$9.65 \cdot 10^4$
.25	7.3	$2.15 \cdot 10^5$
.30	7.9	$4.04 \cdot 10^5$
.35	8.35	$6.75 \cdot 10^5$
.40	8.70	$1.05 \cdot 10^6$
.45	9.0	$1.55 \cdot 10^6$
.50	9.2	$2.17 \cdot 10^6$
.55	9.35	$2.92 \cdot 10^6$
.60	9.5	$3.87 \cdot 10^6$
.65	9.6	$4.98 \cdot 10^6$

By/

(4) Derived from Part I of Interim Report to U.S.W. Panel from the Working Committee (AC.7375/USW.110), August 1944.

By dividing the attenuation values of Table V by the corresponding values of p for $N = 1$ from Table VI, we obtain a set of values of k , the attenuation in db./km. for "homogeneous rain" of intensity 1 mm./hr. By "homogeneous rain" is meant a hypothetical storm in which all the drops are of the same diameter. The values of k found in this way are given in Table VII and are shown graphically in Figures (3) and (4).

Table VII.

Values of k the attenuation in db./km. produced by precipitation at the rate of 1 mm. per hr. of drops all of diameter D .

Temperature 18° C.

$\frac{\lambda}{D}$ cm/g	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	1.0	1.25	3.0	10
.05	1.69	1.175	0.701	0.352	0.112	0.0550	.00853	.000595
.10	1.23	0.925	0.636	0.422	0.136	0.0850	.00687	.000344
.15	0.645	0.628	0.604	0.547	0.204	0.124	.0123	.000278
.20	0.422	0.418	0.411	0.399	0.285	0.142	.0229	.000254
.25	0.296	0.294	0.289	0.286	0.248	0.166	.0320	.000261
.30	0.221	0.220	0.218	0.216	0.210	0.168	.0387	.000280
.35	0.175	0.176	0.179	0.181	0.179	0.170	.0410	.000310
.40	0.145	0.146	0.149	0.150	0.150	0.148	.0415	.000347
.45	0.123	0.124	0.126	0.127	0.128	0.126	.0410	.000395
.50	0.104	0.107	0.108	0.110	0.112	0.110	.0400	.000450
.55	0.0919	0.0950	0.0976	0.0997	0.101	0.0974	.0387	.000517
.60	0.0793	0.0831	0.0870	0.0900	0.0911	0.0851	.0370	.000579
.65	0.0695	0.0754	0.0798	0.0835	0.0845	0.0782	.0350	.000635

The curves of Figures (3) and (4) are, of course, those of Figure (2) multiplied in each case by a factor, which is constant for constant D but varies for different D 's; they must therefore be of the same form and will have limiting values which they must approach as $D/\lambda \rightarrow \infty$ that is, in effect, as $\lambda \rightarrow 0$. These limiting values are marked at the left hand side of Figures (3) and (4).

6. ATTENUATION RELATED TO RATE OF PRECIPITATION FOR ACTUAL STORMS.

In order to compute the attenuation due to an actual rainstorm, we need to know the distribution of the different drop sizes in the storm. If this is known, it can be applied to the k values of Table VII, to find the attenuation produced by the storm as a whole. Typical drop size distributions, associated with different rates of precipitation, have recently been published by Laws & Parsons⁽⁵⁾ and are given here in Table VIII.

Table/

(5) J.O.Laws and D.A.Parsons. loc. cit.
Table VIII is a slightly contracted form of the published data.

Table VIII.

Percentage of Total Precipitation on a Horizontal Surface Contributed by Drops of various sizes. Precipitation p in mm./hr., D in centimetres. (Laws and Parsons).

D	Percentage of Total Volume.							
	0.25 mm/hr.	1.25 mm/hr.	2.5 mm/hr.	12.5 mm/hr.	25 mm/hr.	50 mm/hr.	100 mm/hr.	150 mm/hr.
0.05	26.0	10.9	7.3	2.6	1.7	1.2	1.0	1.0
0.10	50.1	37.1	27.8	11.5	7.6	5.4	4.6	4.1
0.15	18.2	31.3	32.8	24.5	18.4	12.5	8.8	7.6
0.20	3.0	13.5	19.0	25.4	23.9	19.9	13.9	11.7
0.25	0.7	4.9	7.9	17.3	19.9	20.9	17.1	13.9
0.30		1.5	3.3	10.1	12.8	15.6	18.4	17.7
0.35		0.6	1.1	4.3	8.2	10.9	15.0	16.1
0.40		0.2	0.6	2.3	3.5	6.7	9.0	11.9
0.45			0.2	1.2	2.1	3.3	5.8	7.7
0.50				0.6	1.1	1.8	3.0	3.6
0.55				0.2	0.5	1.1	1.7	2.2
0.60					0.3	0.5	1.0	1.2
0.65						0.2	0.7	1.0
0.70								0.3

The distributions of Table VIII are applied to the k values of Table VII to give, for each wavelength, typical values of the db. loss per km. to be expected from rainstorms of different intensity; the results are given in Table IX and Figures (5) and (6).

Table/

Table IX.

Attenuation in db./km. for different rates of
Precipitation of Rain.

Temperature 18° C. λ in cm.

P mm./hr.	Attenuation db./km.									
	$\lambda = 0.3$	$\lambda = 0.4$	$\lambda = 0.5$	$\lambda = 0.6$	$\lambda = 1.0$	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3.0$	$\lambda = 3.2$	$\lambda = 10$	
0.25	0.305	0.230	0.160	0.106	0.037	0.0215	0.00224	0.0019	0.0000997	
1.25	1.15	0.929	0.720	0.549	0.228	0.136	0.0161	0.0117	0.000416	
2.5	1.98	1.66	1.34	1.08	0.492	0.298	0.0388	0.0317	0.000785	
12.5	6.72	6.04	5.36	4.72	2.73	1.77	0.285	0.238	0.00364	
25	11.3	10.4	9.49	8.59	5.47	3.72	0.656	0.555	0.00728	
50	19.2	17.9	16.6	15.3	10.7	7.67	1.46	1.26	0.0149	
100	33.3	31.1	29.0	27.0	20.0	15.3	3.24	2.80	0.0311	
150	46.0	43.7	40.5	37.9	28.8	22.8	4.97	4.39	0.0481	

Since for each D there is a limiting value of k as $D/\lambda \rightarrow \infty$, we can find a corresponding limiting value for the attenuation due to actual storms by applying the size-distributions of Table VIII to the limiting k 's; these values are plotted at the left of Figure (5) and will be seen in each case to be roughly one third of the maximum.

The effect of temperature is discussed in Section (6).

While the work here described was in progress, a series of experimental results by the Bell Telephone Laboratories⁽⁶⁾ was published, for wavelengths of about $\lambda = 0.6$, 1.1 and 3.2 cm. In Figure (7) these results are compared with our computed values. It will be seen that the agreement is excellent.

The close correspondence between the theoretical and experimental curves down to $\lambda = 0.6$ gives confidence in the predicted values of Figure (6) for still shorter wavelengths.

It should be noted that to obtain the total attenuation the contribution due to Oxygen and Water Vapour must, in all cases, be added to the db./km. values given in the report.

7. ATTENUATION DUE TO CLOUDS AND FOGS.

As in Report No. 8516, we shall consider under this heading fogs and clouds composed of fine water droplets, from which no sensible precipitation takes place. In such cases, the predominant diameter of the drops lies between about 0.001 and 0.005 cm. and, as was shown in the above-mentioned report, the expression for the attenuation in db./km. reduces to the very simple form

$$dB/km = 4.093 \frac{M}{\lambda} C_1 \quad \dots (26)$$

where M is the mass, in gms., of liquid water contained in one cubic metre of air and C_1 is a constant given by equation (1) and tabulated in Table IV.

Values of the attenuation derived in this way, for clouds or fogs containing 1 gm. of liquid water per m.³ ($M=1$) are given in Table X. It may be noted that $M=1$ is a reasonable value for dense fogs and clouds, though greater values do occur.

Particularly in the case of fogs, it is sometimes useful to be able to form an estimate of the attenuation directly in terms of the visual range, and a method of determining the probable limits of attenuation associated with any given visual range was developed in Report No. 8516, Section (9).

Table/

(6) G.E.Mueller. B.T.L. Report MM.44-160-150, July 3rd (1944).

Table X.

Attenuation due to Fogs and Clouds
composed of "water Droplets at 18°C.

λ cms.	Attenuation db./km. for M = 1.	$b =$ $\log_{10} 6794 \frac{C_1}{\lambda}$	λ cms.	Attenuation db./km. for M = 1.	$b =$ $\log_{10} 6794 \frac{C_1}{\lambda}$
0.1	13.7	4.338	1.0	0.438	2.661
0.2	7.14	4.074	1.1	0.371	2.789
0.3	3.97	3.819	1.2	0.305	2.704
0.4	2.48	3.614	1.25	0.280	2.668
0.5	1.65	3.438	2.0	0.112	2.270
0.6	1.17	3.288	3.0	0.0499	1.919
0.7	0.876	3.163	5.0	0.0178	1.471
0.8	0.671	3.047	10.0	0.00450	0.873
0.9	0.536	2.949			

Briefly, it was found from published observations that, if $\bar{M}$ is the mean value of M associated with a visual range S, expressed in feet, then

$$\bar{M} = 1660 S^{-1.43} \quad \dots(27)$$

and that, in 95% of cases, the actual value of M lies between $\frac{1}{2}\bar{M}$ and $2\bar{M}$.

Substituting in (26), we find that the mean attenuation in db./km. associated with the visual range S, is given by

$$\log_{10} \text{db./km} = b - 1.43 \log_{10} S \quad \dots(28)$$

where

$$b = \log_{10} 6794 \frac{C_1}{\lambda} \quad \dots(29)$$

Values of b are given in Table X and the corresponding limits of attenuation associated with various visual ranges are given in Table XI, for the wavelengths 0.5, 1.25, 3.0 cms.

The effect of temperature variation is discussed in Section (9).

Table XI.

Limits of Attenuation associated with given
Visual Range in Fog and Cloud.

Temperature 18° C.

Visual Range in Cloud or Fog.	M gm./m. ³	Attenuation in db./km.		
		$\lambda = 0.5$ cm.	$\lambda = 1.25$ cm.	$\lambda = 3.0$ cm.
100 ft.	2.3	1.9 - 7.6	0.32 - 1.3	0.058 - 0.23
200	0.85	0.70- 2.8	0.12 -0.48	0.021 - 0.085
300	0.48	0.39- 1.6	0.069-0.28	0.012 - 0.048
400	0.32	0.26- 1.0	0.044-0.18	0.0079- 0.032
500	0.23	0.19-0.76	0.032-0.13	0.0058- 0.023
750	0.13	0.11-0.42	0.018-0.072	0.0032- 0.013
1000	0.085	0.070-0.28	0.012-0.048	0.0021- 0.0085
2000	0.032	0.025-0.10	0.0044-0.018	0.00079- 0.0032
3000	0.018	0.015-0.058	0.0025-0.010	0.00044- 0.0018

8. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON ATTENUATION DUE TO RAINFALL.

For the wavelengths 0.5, 1.25, 3.0 and 10 cms., each stage in the computations of attenuation due to rainfall, described in previous sections, was repeated for the temperatures 0° C. and 40° C., using the appropriate values of n and n_{λ} taken from Table I.

The final results, expressed as db. loss per km. for a given rate of precipitation, are given in Tables XII, XIII, XIV; the values for intermediate temperatures have been found by graphical interpolation.

Table XII.

Effect of Temperature on Attenuation due
to Rainfall. $\lambda = 0.5$ cm.

Rate of Precipitation mm./hr.	Attenuation in db./km.					
	0° C.	10° C.	18° C.	20° C.	30° C.	40° C.
0.25	0.135	0.150	0.160	0.161	0.164	0.158
1.25	0.626	0.696	0.720	0.730	0.750	0.733
2.5	1.17	1.27	1.34	1.35	1.38	1.36
12.5	4.82	5.15	5.36	5.40	5.49	5.37
25	8.67	9.20	9.49	9.54	9.62	9.46
50	15.5	16.2	16.6	16.6	16.8	16.5
100	27.6	28.5	29.0	29.0	29.2	28.9
150	38.8	39.8	40.5	40.5	40.8	40.4

Table XIII.

Effect of Temperature on Attenuation due to Rainfall.

$$\lambda = 1.25 \text{ cm.}$$

Rate of Precipitation mm./hr.	Attenuation in db. per km.					
	0° C.	10° C.	18° C.	20° C.	30° C.	40° C.
0.25	0.020	0.021	0.021	0.021	0.019	0.017
1.25	0.117	0.132	0.136	0.135	0.125	0.108
2.5	0.252	0.295	0.298	0.295	0.273	0.239
12.5	1.47	1.70	1.77	1.76	1.65	1.43
25	3.08	3.55	3.72	3.72	3.55	3.03
50	6.44	7.25	7.67	7.67	7.25	6.33
100	13.0	14.7	15.3	13.5	14.7	13.0
150	19.5	21.9	22.8	22.8	22.0	19.7

Table XIV.

Effect of Temperature on Attenuation due to Rainfall.

$$\lambda = 3.2 \text{ cm.}$$

Rate of Precipitation mm./hr.	Attenuation in db. per km.					
	0° C.	10° C.	18° C.	20° C.	30° C.	40° C.
0.25	0.00228	0.00208	0.00188	0.00182	0.00148	0.00104
1.25	0.0126	0.0123	0.0117	0.0115	0.00100	0.00772
2.5	0.0258	0.0320	0.0317	0.0310	0.0260	0.0203
12.5	0.152	0.210	0.238	0.237	0.215	0.167
25.0	0.342	0.475	0.555	0.56	0.54	0.417
50	0.779	1.10	1.26	1.27	1.24	1.02
100	1.79	2.44	2.80	2.85	2.63	2.41
150	2.91	3.87	4.39	4.48	4.54	3.91

Table/

Table XV.

Effect of Temperature on Attenuation due to
Rainfall.

$$\lambda = 10 \text{ cm.}$$

Rate of Precipitation mm./hr.	Attenuation in db. per km.					
	0° C.	10° C.	18° C.	20° C.	30° C.	40° C.
0.25	.000201	.000140	.0000997	.0000947	.0000700	.0000591
1.25	.000842	.000582	.000416	.000395	.000292	.000245
2.50	.00159	.00110	.000785	.000745	.000550	.000461
12.5	.00734	.00510	.00364	.00346	.00255	.00212
25.0	.0146	.0102	.00728	.00691	.00501	.00423
50.0	.0298	.0208	.0149	.0142	.0104	.00865
100.0	.0622	.0435	.0311	.0296	.0218	.0181
150.0	.0962	.0674	.0481	.0456	.0337	.0282

The general character of the temperature effect is brought out more clearly if the variations are expressed in the form of a correction factor $\phi(T)$, which is to be applied to the standard results of Table IX, to give the attenuation at temperatures other than 18° C. This has been done for five rates of precipitation and the results are given in Table XVI.

A study of this table shows that, in general, we may conclude that the temperature effect is much less marked at the shorter than at the longer wavelengths. For $\lambda = 3$ cms. or less the variations in the temperature range 10° C. - 30° C. do not exceed 10%, except for the very lightest rain, but for $\lambda = 10$ cm. the values for 10° C. and 30° C. are respectively 40% greater and 30% less than those for 18° C. These facts are easily understood when it is realized that, for any wavelength, the temperature effect is greatest for small values of λ and becomes very small when λ is large; further, here we keep the same values of D for all wavelengths, so that α is inversely proportional to λ .

Table/

Table XVI.

Temperature Correction Factor $\phi(T)$ to be applied to Table IX to give the Attenuation due to Rainstorms, at various Temperatures.

Rate of Precipitation mm. per hr.	λ	Correction Factor $\phi(T)$				
		T=0°C.	T=10°C.	T=18°C.	T=30°C.	T=40°C.
0.25	0.5	0.85	0.95	1.0	1.02	0.99
	1.25	0.95	1.0	1.0	0.90	0.81
	3.2	1.21	1.10	1.0	0.79	0.55
	10.0	2.01	1.40	1.0	0.70	0.59
2.5	0.5	0.87	0.95	1.0	1.03	1.01
	1.25	0.85	0.99	1.0	0.92	0.80
	3.2	0.82	1.01	1.0	0.82	0.64
	10.0	2.02	1.40	1.0	0.70	0.59
12.5	0.5	0.90	0.96	1.0	1.02	1.00
	1.25	0.83	0.96	1.0	0.93	0.81
	3.2	0.64	0.88	1.0	0.90	0.70
	10.0	2.03	1.40	1.0	0.70	0.59
50	0.5	0.94	0.98	1.0	1.01	1.00
	1.25	0.84	0.95	1.0	0.95	0.83
	3.2	0.62	0.87	1.0	0.99	0.81
	10.0	2.01	1.40	1.0	0.70	0.58
150	0.5	0.96	0.98	1.0	1.01	1.00
	1.25	0.86	0.96	1.0	0.97	0.87
	3.2	0.66	0.88	1.0	1.03	0.89
	10.0	2.00	1.40	1.0	0.70	0.58

9. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON ATTENUATION DUE TO FOGS AND CLOUDS.

For the wavelengths 0.5, 1.25, 3.2 and 10 cms. the values of the constant C_1 were determined for the temperatures 0, 10, 30 and 40° C., using the appropriate values of n and nX given in Table I.

It is convenient to express the results in the form

$$C_{1(T)} = \phi_1(T) C_{1(18^\circ)} \quad \dots(30)$$

where C_1 is the value for 18° C., given in Table IV, for

then/

then $\phi_c(T)$ will also be the correction factor to be applied to the attenuations given in Tables X and XI; the constant b is to be corrected by the addition of $\log_{10} \phi_c(T)$.

The values of $\phi_c(T)$ for the four wavelengths specified are given in Table XVII.

Table XVII.

Temperature Correction Factor $\phi_c(T)$
for Attenuation due to Clouds and Fogs.

λ	Correction Factor $\phi_c(T)$					
	0°C.	10°C.	18°C.	20°C.	30°C.	40°C.
0.5	1.59	1.20	1.0	0.95	0.73	0.59
1.25	1.93	1.29	1.0	0.95	0.73	0.57
3.2	1.98	1.30	1.0	0.95	0.70	0.56
10.0	2.0	1.25	1.0	0.95	0.67	0.59

10. ATTENUATION FOR HAILSTONES AT A CONCENTRATION OF 1 PER CM.³ (N=1).

The computation of the attenuation due to hailstones follows the same general lines as that for water drops, but the very much smaller values of the constants n and $\alpha\chi$, see Table II, allow certain simplifications to be used.

In this case the series form of Report No. 8516, Section (3), is valid up to about $\alpha\chi = 0.5$ and moreover, since χ^2 may be neglected, the coefficients C_1 , C_2 and C_3 of that equation reduce to the following simple forms, the first two of which are proportional to χ .

$$C_1 = \chi \frac{12n^2}{(n^2+2)^2} \dots\dots(31)$$

$$C_2 = \chi \left[\frac{12n^2(7n^2-10)}{5(n^2+2)^3} + \frac{10n^2}{3(2n^2+3)^2} + \frac{2n^2}{15} \right] \dots\dots(32)$$

$$C_3 = \frac{4(n^2-1)^2}{3(n^2+2)^2} \dots\dots(33)$$

Substituting the value $n = 1.75$ in these expressions we then have

$$f_1(\alpha) = \alpha^3 (1.43\chi + 1.18\chi\alpha^2 + 0.221\alpha^3 \dots) \dots\dots(34)$$

for all values of α up to 0.5.

It will be seen that, for very small values of α , $f_1(\alpha)$ will be proportional to χ , while for much larger values of α , $f_1(\alpha)$ will be nearly independent of χ .

For values of α greater than 0.5, it is necessary to compute $f_1(\alpha)$ from the exact expressions in the manner outlined in Section (3) of the present report. Since, however, $f_1(\alpha)$ is now practically independent of χ , it is possible to use the simpler expressions (9) and (10) to determine q_v and p_v , instead of the more complicated (19) and (20) and thus to avoid the very considerable labour of evaluating G and H. The accuracy of the values obtained by neglecting χ in this way was checked at several points by comparison with the results obtained from the full computation and it was found that, at least as far as $\alpha = 4$, the error did not exceed 1 per cent.

The results obtained in this way for hailstones at 0° C. and at a concentration of 1 per cm^3 are given in Table XVIII and are shown graphically in Figure 8.

Table XVIII.

Attenuation in db./km. produced by Dry Hailstones of Diameter D at a Concentration of 1 Drop per cm^3
(N = 1).

Temperature 0° C.

D cms.	Attenuation in db./km. for N=1.			
	$\lambda = 0.5$	$\lambda = 1.25$	$\lambda = 3.2$	$\lambda = 10$
.05	3.75	$2.81 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$7.43 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.29 \cdot 10^{-2}$
.10	$3.16 \cdot 10^2$	7.57	$7.15 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.85 \cdot 10^{-1}$
.15	$3.98 \cdot 10^3$	$7.41 \cdot 10^1$	3.57	$6.35 \cdot 10^{-1}$
.20	$1.41 \cdot 10^4$	$4.00 \cdot 10^2$	$1.37 \cdot 10^1$	1.57
.25	$4.07 \cdot 10^4$	$1.23 \cdot 10^3$	$4.36 \cdot 10^1$	3.24
.30	$8.91 \cdot 10^4$	$3.31 \cdot 10^3$	$1.19 \cdot 10^2$	5.99
.35	$1.41 \cdot 10^5$	$8.91 \cdot 10^3$	$2.85 \cdot 10^2$	$1.06 \cdot 10^1$
.40	$1.79 \cdot 10^5$	$2.53 \cdot 10^4$	$6.15 \cdot 10^2$	$1.80 \cdot 10^1$
.45	$2.24 \cdot 10^5$	$5.13 \cdot 10^4$	$1.22 \cdot 10^3$	$2.93 \cdot 10^1$
.50	$2.63 \cdot 10^5$	$9.55 \cdot 10^4$	$2.27 \cdot 10^3$	$4.64 \cdot 10^1$
.75	$4.07 \cdot 10^5$	$6.31 \cdot 10^5$	$2.63 \cdot 10^4$	$3.24 \cdot 10^2$
1.00	$4.08 \cdot 10^5$	$1.59 \cdot 10^6$	$1.59 \cdot 10^5$	$1.67 \cdot 10^3$
1.25		$2.51 \cdot 10^6$	$5.01 \cdot 10^5$	$5.89 \cdot 10^3$
1.50		$2.69 \cdot 10^6$	$1.18 \cdot 10^6$	$1.70 \cdot 10^4$
2.0			$3.98 \cdot 10^6$	$9.77 \cdot 10^4$
3.0			$1.45 \cdot 10^7$	$1.10 \cdot 10^6$
4.0			$1.79 \cdot 10^7$	$5.37 \cdot 10^6$

11. ATTENUATION PRODUCED BY ACTUAL HAILSTORMS.

Following the same procedure as in the case of rain, we next determine values of k , the attenuation in db./km. produced by unit rate of precipitation. To find this we need the terminal velocity of hailstones. Humphreys⁽⁷⁾ states, in effect, that this velocity is 59 miles per hour for stones one inch in diameter and 116 miles per hour for stones of three inches diameter. It should be noted that, owing to the inclusion of air in the alternate shells, the density is of the order of 0.8. For very small stones we have used the terminal velocity for rain drops, adjusted to allow for the difference in density; for intermediate sizes, values have been found by graphical interpolation. The results are given in Table XIX.

If these terminal velocities are substituted in (25), we obtain values of the precipitation in mm. of ice per hour, which may be converted to mm./hr. of liquid water by the factor 0.8. These values of p , for the standard concentration $N = 1$, are also shown in Table XIX. Dividing the values of Table XVIII by the p values for $N = 1$ we obtain k , the attenuation in db./km. produced by a rate of precipitation of hail which, if the ice were melted, would amount to 1 mm./hr. of liquid water. These values are given in Table XIX. No size-distribution functions for hailstones are available but, fortunately, their diameter range at any moment is generally much less than in the case of rain. This being so, a fair estimate of the attenuation due to any actual precipitation may be found by multiplying the observed equivalent precipitation rate by the k for the predominant stone size.

Table XIX.

Values of k for Hailstones (density 0.8).
 k = Attenuation in db./km. for a precipitation equivalent to 1 mm./hr. of water.

D cms.	v m/sec.	p for $N=1$.	k = Attenuation in db./km. for $p = 1$.			
			$\lambda = 0.5$ cms.	$\lambda = 1.25$ cms.	$\lambda = 3.2$ cms.	$\lambda = 10$ cms.
0.1	3.1	$4.70 \cdot 10^3$	$6.74 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.54 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$3.94 \cdot 10^{-5}$
0.2	5.1	$6.18 \cdot 10^4$	$2.27 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$6.48 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.22 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.54 \cdot 10^{-5}$
0.3	7.0	$2.87 \cdot 10^5$	$3.11 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.59 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.14 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.08 \cdot 10^{-5}$
0.4	8.1	$7.82 \cdot 10^5$	$2.29 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$3.23 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.85 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.30 \cdot 10^{-5}$
0.5	9.2	$1.74 \cdot 10^6$	$1.51 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$5.50 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.66 \cdot 10^{-5}$
0.75	12.0	$7.64 \cdot 10^6$	$5.34 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$8.27 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.44 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$4.25 \cdot 10^{-5}$
1.0	15.0	$2.23 \cdot 10^7$	$1.82 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.13 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$7.13 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.50 \cdot 10^{-5}$
1.5	19.0	$9.69 \cdot 10^7$		$2.78 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-4}$
2.0	22.8	$2.72 \cdot 10^8$			$1.46 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.56 \cdot 10^{-4}$
3.0	29.5	$1.20 \cdot 10^9$			$1.21 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$9.16 \cdot 10^{-4}$
4.0	35.5	$3.42 \cdot 10^9$			$5.24 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-3}$

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(7)

W.J.Humphreys. Physics of the Air. p.346 (1929).

At this point it is of interest to compare the attenuation produced by hail with that due to rain. For this purpose, we shall assume the diameters of the stones and drops to be equal. Table XX shows the ratios, first for equal concentrations N and second for equal rates of precipitation.

Table XX.

Ratio of Rates of Attenuation produced by Hail to that due to Rain.

	D cm.	$\lambda=0.5$ cm.	$\lambda=1.25$ cm.	$\lambda=3.2$ cm.	$\lambda=10$ cm.
Fixed Concentration N	0.1	0.068	0.012	0.016	0.073
	0.2	0.36	0.029	0.010	0.063
	0.3	1.01	0.044	0.010	0.053
	0.4	1.14	0.16	0.015	0.049
	0.5	1.11	0.40	0.029	0.048
Fixed Precipitation Rate	0.1	0.11	0.019	0.025	0.11
	0.2	0.56	0.046	0.013	0.10
	0.3	1.40	0.085	0.012	0.075
	0.4	1.53	0.22	0.021	0.066
	0.5	1.36	0.50	0.036	0.060

The ratios in the case of constant rate of precipitation are more irregular than when N is fixed because of the complication introduced by the varying terminal velocities.

12. EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON ATTENUATION DUE TO DRY HAILSTONES.

Since for ice the constant n is independent of temperature and, for $\alpha > 0.5$, $f_1(\alpha)$ is independent of χ , it follows that the attenuation will not be affected by temperature, when the particles are large.

For very small values of α , on the other hand, $f_1(\alpha)$ is proportional to χ and the attenuation will therefore depend on temperature in the same way as χ . As α is increased, the temperature effect will gradually diminish, until it practically disappears at about $\alpha = 0.5$.

The value $\alpha = 0.5$ corresponds to about $D = 1.5, 0.5, 0.2$ and 0.08 cms. for $\lambda = 10, 3.2, 1.25, 0.5$ cms. respectively. It will be seen, therefore, that the temperature effect is negligible for hailstorms when $\lambda = 1.25$ cms. or less but that it may be significant for storms composed of small hailstones when λ is equal to or greater than 3 cms.

The correction factors $\phi_3(T)$ to be applied to the attenuation values for 0°C . given in Tables XVIII and XIX are shown in Figure 9.

13. ATTENUATION DUE TO CLOUDS COMPOSED OF ICE PARTICLES.

As in the case of water droplet clouds, we can use equation (26). Further, since χ is small, we can write equation (1) for C_1 in the form

$$C_1 = \chi \frac{12 n^2}{(n^2 + 2)^2} \quad (\text{Spherules}) \dots\dots(35)$$

while equations (17) and (18) of Report No. 8516, for needles and discs respectively, reduce to

$$C_1 = \chi \frac{4n^2}{9} \left\{ 1 + \frac{8}{(n^2 + 1)^2} \right\} (\text{Needles}) \dots\dots(36)$$

$$C_1 = \chi \frac{4n^2}{9} \left\{ 2 + \frac{1}{n^2} \right\} (\text{Discs}) \dots\dots(37)$$

From Table II, we see that n is independent of both λ and temperature and has the value 1.75 so that

$$C_1 = 1.43 \chi \quad (\text{Spherules}) \dots\dots(38)$$

$$C_1 = 2.02 \chi \quad (\text{Needles}) \dots\dots(39)$$

$$C_1 = 2.86 \chi \quad (\text{Discs}) \dots\dots(40)$$

Substituting in (26), we find the following values of the attenuation in db./km.

Table XXI.

Attenuation in db./km. for Ice Crystal Clouds.

	T = -40° C.	T = 0° C.
Spherules	0.00044 $\frac{M}{\lambda}$	0.0035 $\frac{M}{\lambda}$
Needles	0.00062 $\frac{M}{\lambda}$	0.0050 $\frac{M}{\lambda}$
Discs	0.00087 $\frac{M}{\lambda}$	0.0070 $\frac{M}{\lambda}$

It may be noted that, for ice clouds, the value of M will rarely exceed 0.5 and will often be less than 0.1.

The new values of the ice constants have resulted in the reduction to one third, or less, of the attenuations given previously in Report No. 8516; these earlier values were for 0° C. only.

It will be seen that for a λ of about 1 cm., the attenuation produced by ice particle clouds at 0° C. will be

of the order of $1/200^{\text{th}}$ that of water droplet clouds, at the same temperature and water content. Similarly, for ice clouds at -40° C. the attenuation will be only $1/2000^{\text{th}}$ that of corresponding liquid droplet clouds at 0° C.

It may be concluded that the attenuation produced by ice clouds is so small that it may almost always be neglected.

14. FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE OF THE HIGHER PRECIPITATION RATES.

Detailed data, giving the frequency of rainfall of given intensity and duration in the Pacific Area, have been prepared by the Working Committee. These data, with the rainfall intensity converted into attenuation by means of the Tables computed here, will form the subject of a separate report from the Working Committee.

The present section is intended to supplement this, by providing information on the higher rates of precipitation, and therefore of attenuation, that may be experienced on occasion.

First we shall consider the greatest mean rates of rainfall that have been observed to occur, for a given duration, anywhere in the world; these we shall refer to as World Records. Second, we shall consider the corresponding record rates for the British Isles, together with some outstanding cases in particular localities. The chief sources from which the rainfall intensities and durations have been obtained are Bilham⁽⁸⁾ for the British Isles and Tennehill⁽⁹⁾ for the World Records. Additional data have been extracted from other sources⁽¹⁰⁾. The World Record for short period rain is the storm which occurred at Porto Bello, U.S.A. Atlantic Coast Central Zone, on November 29th 1911. The storm lasted for about 2 hours, during which the average rate of rainfall was 80 mm./hr. This in itself by no means constitutes a record, but during one particular 3 minutes the rate rose to the extraordinarily high value of 1,260 mm./hr.

The World Records for long period continuous heavy rain are as follows. At Baguio in the Philippines there occurred in July 1911, a storm which lasted for 4 days, during which the average rate for the heaviest 24 hours was 49 mm./hr; this constitutes a World Record

for/

(8) E.G. Bilham. The Climate of the British Isles (1938).
Macmillan.

(9) I.R. Tennehill. Weather Around the World (1943).
Princeton University Press.

(10) Bartholemew's Meteorological Atlas, Vol. III.
Also "Atlas of British Rainfall" and
"British Rainfall". H.M.S.O.

for the given duration. The average rate for the whole four days was 23 mm./hr. but this was exceeded in a four-day storm at Silver Hill in Jamaica, during which the average rate was 25 mm./hr. Finally, the record for a three-day storm occurred at Funkiko in Formosa, for which the average rate was 29 mm./hr.

These values, together with two other rates just short of the 24-hour record, are shown in Figure (10), on which the log of the rate in mm./hr. is plotted against the log of the duration t in hours.

As regards the British Isles, Bilham quotes from British Rainfall (1935) a table of rainfalls of very exceptional intensity, lasting for periods up to one hour. These are the greatest recorded in the years 1875 to 1935. In Figure (10) the highest rate corresponding to given durations are plotted; when more than one occurrence is listed, the two highest rates are included in the plot. For the longer periods, we may take the case of the thunderstorm at Cannington, Somerset, on August 18th 1924, during which 240 mm. fell. Of this amount, 203 mm. fell in 5 hours, giving a rate of 40.5 mm./hr. This case is also plotted.

It will be seen that not only do these record values fall approximately on straight lines but, what is somewhat unexpected, the lines for the World and British Isles records are roughly parallel.

For practical purposes we can take these two lines as representing the maximum average rates of rainfall extending over any given duration from 5 minutes to 100 hours.

In general, high rates of rainfall for the shorter periods are associated with thunderstorms while cyclonic rains, although producing a greater total rainfall, seldom attain the very high intensities.

Bilham quotes the exceptional Norwich storm of 25-26 August 1912, for which the average rate was 8.5 mm./hr. over the whole 24 hours. In this storm more than 100 mm. of rain fell over an area of about 1660 sq. miles. It will be seen that, although an exceptional storm, the corresponding point on Figure (10) falls far below the British Isles record intensity line, which may be assumed to be associated with thunderstorms. It may be of interest to add, for comparison, that in the Cannington (Somerset) thunderstorm, also plotted, the area over which more than 100 mm. of rain fell was only some 10 sq. miles in extent.

Next, we shall consider intensities of rainfall which may be expected to occur more frequently, for example once in three months to once per year in England and Wales.

From Bilham's expression (Climate of the British Isles, p.118) we deduce that

$$\log_{10} \left[\frac{p}{t} + 152.4 \right] = 2.43 + 0.282 \log_{10} \frac{t}{N} \quad \dots (41)$$

where N is the average number of occasions per year that, at a given average station in England and Wales, the rate of precipitation will attain or exceed p mm./hr. throughout a

period/

period of t minutes.

Three curves, plotted from the above relation, are shown in Figure (10) for $N = 1/10, 1$ and 4 respectively. These curves serve to determine the likely rates of the heavier rains in England and Wales.

From the climatological data given by Best (11) for stations in Sumatra, Java, Borneo etc. corresponding lines can be drawn on the diagram for each locality. This has been done in Figure (11) for a frequency of once a year; the shaded area includes all the lines, which incidentally have various slopes, for the localities stated. On the left hand side of this Figure three scales are given, to enable values of the attenuation to be read directly for the wavelengths of 0.5, 1.25 and 3.2 cm. It must be emphasised that, to obtain the total attenuation, the contribution due to Oxygen and Water Vapour must be added; this is particularly important for the 0.5 cm. case and for the lower attenuation values at the other wavelengths. Since the size-distribution data of Lewis and Parsons extend only up to 150 mm/hr., the higher values of the attenuation scales were determined by logarithmic extrapolation and must therefore be regarded as approximate.

Figure (12) is similar to Figure (11) but gives data for frequencies of twelve times a year.

(11) Interim Report of the Working Committee, Part I. loc.cit.

TYPED BY: DB.
CHECKED BY: DR.
APPROVED BY: JWR.

C.C.PATERSON.
DIRECTOR.
RESEARCH LABORATORIES.

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ATTENUATION COEFFICIENT

$$\sigma = \frac{N\lambda^2}{2\pi} f_1(\alpha)$$

VALUES OF
 $f_1(\alpha)$ FOR $\lambda = 0.3 \text{ cm}$
SEE EQU. (2)

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FIG. 1.

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ATTENUATION IN db/km
PRODUCED BY RAINDROPS
AT A CONCENTRATION OF
1 DROP PER CM³.

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FIG 2

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VALUES OF k THE
ATTENUATION IN db/km
PRODUCED BY A
PRECIPITATION OF IMM/HR.
OF RAIN OF DROP
DIAMETER DCM.

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DATE 24-5-45

FIG. 3

VALUES OF k THE
ATTENUATION IN db/km
PRODUCED BY A
PRECIPITATION OF 1mm/hr
OF RAIN OF DROP
DIAMETER D cm.

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FIG. 4.

FIG. 5.

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ATTENUATION IN $db/\lambda m$
PRODUCED BY RAINSTORMS.

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FIG. 6.

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ATTENUATION IN db/km
PRODUCED BY RAINSTORMS
COMPARISON OF PREDICTED
AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

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FIG. 7.

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ATTENUATION PRODUCED
BY HAILSTONES OF
DIAMETER D CM. AT A
CONCENTRATION OF $N=1$.

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FIG. 8.

DATE 24-5-45

FIG. 9.

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RATES OF PRECIPITATION,
IN RAINSTORMS,
WHICH ARE ATTAINED OR EXCEEDED
FOR GIVEN DURATIONS.

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FIG. 10.

DATE 24-5-45

RATES OF PRECIPITATION IN RAINSTORMS, AND THE CONSEQUENT ATTENUATIONS,

WHICH ARE ATTAINED OR EXCEEDED,
FOR GIVEN DURATIONS,
WITH AN AVERAGE FREQUENCY
OF ONCE PER YEAR

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FIG. 11

DATE 24 5 45.

RATES OF PRECIPITATION IN RAINSTORMS, AND THE CONSEQUENT ATTENUATIONS,

WHICH ARE ATTAINED OR EXCEEDED
FOR GIVEN DURATIONS

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FIG. 12

